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Efficacy of Mindfulness-Based Art Therapy for Reducing Stress in Adolescents

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Abstract

Mindfulness-Based Art Therapy (MBAT) is a combination of mindfulness practices adapted from Mindfulness-Based Stress Reduction and Art Therapy. MBAT is a psychosocial intervention that incorporates mindfulness skills training and creating art images designed to enhance awareness and understanding of oneself. The preliminary studies regarding MBAT suggest that it is beneficial in ameliorating psychological symptoms associated with stressors. To provide evidence to its efficacy, a quasi-experimental approach was employed, specifically the one-group pretest-posttest design. Perceived Stress Scale-10 (PSS-10) was used to measure the dependent variable of the study, a standard measurement of stress with superior psychometric properties. The sample comprised of adolescence ($N = 43$) with moderately and highly perceived stress scores on PSS-10. The participants received one session of MBAT guided by an adopted manual. The data were analyzed using Paired Samples T-Test, accompanied by Cohen's D to measure effect size. The results showed statistical significant improvements between pretest and posttest ($t(32) = 12.6$, $p < .001$) with an extremely large effect size ($g = 2.20$). The results indicate that MBAT is an effective treatment in reducing the stress of adolescents.

Keywords: *stress, Mindfulness-Based Art Therapy, adolescents*

Introduction

Mindfulness-Based Art Therapy (MBAT) combines mindfulness practices derived from Mindfulness-Based Stress Reduction with Art Therapy. It is a psychosocial intervention that integrates training in mindfulness skills with the creation of art, aimed at enhancing self-awareness and self-understanding. Preliminary studies on MBAT suggest its effectiveness in reducing psychological symptoms linked to stressors (Kennedy, 2003). The concept of mindfulness centers around an individual's awareness of the present moment, achieved through various meditation techniques. For instance, mindfulness breathing involves focusing on one's breath rhythm to release present worries (Cho, Noh, Lee, & Ryu, 2020), while compassion-focused meditation encourages kindness and understanding through repeated phrases (Kirby, 2016). These mindfulness practices are particularly beneficial during crises, aiding in the reduction of psychological symptoms such as stress, anxiety, and depression (Behan, 2020; Khendelwal, 2020).

Research on students has demonstrated that daily mindfulness breathing exercises can reduce test anxiety and foster positive thinking (Cho, Noh, Lee, & Ryu, 2020). Similarly, studies exploring the use of mindfulness meditation mobile applications among students have shown significant reductions in stress levels and increases in self-compassion (Huberty et al., 2019). In controlled experiments, mindfulness-based programs have been found effective in reducing symptoms of depression and anxiety, thereby enhancing students' overall quality of life (Lahtinen & Salmivalli, 2020).

Stress is a natural biological response to the demands we face both internally and externally in our daily lives. While everyone experiences stress, its severity and duration vary due to different factors. There are two primary types of stress: acute stress and chronic stress (Legg, 2020). Acute stress is the immediate physiological reaction to perceived danger. It typically occurs briefly and subsides once the perceived threat disappears. Acute stress does not usually lead to long-term issues for individuals. Examples of acute stressors include sudden events like traffic jams, job interviews, medical appointments, long lines at banks, heavy rainstorms, and earthquakes (Garfin, Thompson, & Holman, 2018; Barber, Khol, Kassam-Adams, & Gold, 2014). Conversely, chronic stress is characterized by prolonged and constant feelings of stress that significantly impact an individual's physical and mental well-being (Scott & Susman, 2020). It persists over an extended period, and its severity often hinges on how well stress symptoms are managed. Chronic stress typically arises from unaddressed acute stress; for instance, repeated daily exposure to acute stressors without adequate coping mechanisms or resources can lead to chronic stress. Common causes include living in poverty, residing in high-crime areas, familial difficulties, chronic illness, persistent life-threatening situations, academic pressures, substance abuse, toxic work environments, imbalance between work and personal life, unemployment, and natural disasters (Boudreau, Johnson, & Herman, 2011).

Research Questions

The study aimed to assess the effectiveness of mindfulness-based art therapy in reducing stress among adolescents. Specifically, it measured the average stress levels of distance learning students before and after participating in mindfulness-based art therapy, and evaluated the significant difference in stress scores between pretest and posttest measurements.

Methodology

Research Design

The researcher utilized a quasi-experimental approach was employed, specifically the one-group pretest-posttest design. In this design,

the researcher measured the scores of one-group before and after administering the treatment, then the difference between the pretest and posttest scores was compared (Allen, 2017).

Participants

A total of 43 adolescents from Christian Mission Services Philippines in Tanza, Cavite, met the eligibility criteria and were included in the study, comprising 16 males and 27 females. Inclusion criteria required participants to be: (1) aged between 10 and 19 years, (2) proficient in reading and understanding English, and (3) scoring moderate (≥ 14) or high (≥ 27) on the Perceived Stress Scale-10. Exclusion criteria included: (1) reluctance to participate in research, (2) previous exposure to stress-reducing therapy, (3) current participation in psychotherapy, (4) current use of psychopharmacological treatment, (5) diagnosed with psychological or psychiatric disorders, and (6) medical conditions contributing to elevated stress levels.

Instruments

The Perceived Stress Scale-10 (PSS-10) was utilized as the primary measure of the study's dependent variable. Developed by Dr. Sheldon Cohen, the PSS-10 is a widely used instrument in stress-related research and experiments. It consists of 10 questions assessing various stress-related situations. Scores on the PSS-10 range from 0 to 40, with scores categorized as low stress (0-13), moderate stress (14-26), and high stress (27-40). Responses are rated on a 5-point scale (0 = never to 4 = very often). The PSS-10 demonstrates robust psychometric properties, including a Cronbach's alpha coefficient of .82 and a test-retest reliability coefficient of .77 over a 2-week interval (Lee, 2012). It has shown consistent reliability across various test-retest intervals: 2 days (Cohen, Kamarck, & Mermelstein, 1983), 1 week (Chaaya et al., 2010), 2 weeks (Almadi et al., 2012), 4 weeks (Wongpakaran & Wongpakaran, 2010), and 6 weeks (Cohen, Kamarck, & Mermelstein, 1983). This reliability ensures that the PSS-10 maintains accuracy and dependability across different test administrations (Marx et al., 2003), establishing it as a robust health-related instrument with excellent internal consistency and validity.

Procedure

Prior to participating in the MBAT session, the respondents' stress levels were assessed using the PSS-10. Following the intervention, the same stress assessment was administered to gauge changes in perceived stress. The collected data were analyzed using statistical methods, specifically the Paired Samples T-Test, which compares the means of two related groups (pretest and posttest). Additionally, Cohen's D was utilized to determine the effect size of the observed changes.

Data Analysis

The Shapiro-Wilk Test of Normality was employed to assess the normality of the data. Paired Samples T-Test was used to compare the stress levels of adolescence between the pretest and posttest, and to determine the statistically significant difference in scores. Hedges' G was utilized to calculate the effect size, providing insight into the practical significance of the Paired Samples T-Test results. Statistical analysis was conducted using Jamovi software under the APGL3 license.

Results and Discussion

Table 1. *Shapiro Wilk Test of Normality*

	<i>W</i>	<i>p</i>
Pretest - Posttest	0.938	0.061

The Shapiro-Wilk test of normality yielded a p-value of 0.061 for the comparison between the pretest and posttest data. This result suggests that the research data does not significantly deviate from a normal distribution at the conventional significance level (typically set at $\alpha = 0.05$). Therefore, based on the Shapiro-Wilk test, there is no strong evidence to reject the assumption of normality for the pretest and posttest data.

Table 2. *Paired Samples T-Test*

	<i>t</i>	<i>df</i>	<i> t </i>	<i>d</i>
Pretest - Posttest	12.6	32	.001	2.20

The results of the study revealed significant improvements in stress levels among distance learning students ($N = 43$) who participated in a single session of Mindfulness-Based Art Therapy (MBAT). The application of the Paired Samples T-Test indicated a strong statistical significance ($t(32) = 12.6, p < .001$) between pretest and posttest stress scores. Moreover, the effect size, as measured by Cohen's D, was found to be extremely large ($g = 2.20$), underscoring the substantial reduction in perceived stress levels following the MBAT intervention.

These findings suggest that the integration of mindfulness practices and art therapy techniques in MBAT holds promise as an effective treatment for reducing stress among adolescents. The observed improvements in stress levels indicate the potential of MBAT to ameliorate psychological symptoms associated with stressors, thus offering an innovative and holistic approach to enhancing adolescents' well-being.

Conclusions

The purpose of this study was to examine the effectiveness of mindfulness-based art therapy (MBAT) as a psychosocial intervention for reducing stress in teenagers. MBAT integrates mindfulness exercises derived from Mindfulness-Based Stress Reduction with art therapy methods, offering a unique approach to enhancing self-awareness and understanding. This investigation was inspired by preliminary studies suggesting that MBAT positively impacts stress-related psychological symptoms.

Using a one-group pretest-posttest design, the study assessed the immediate effect of a single MBAT session on perceived stress levels. The results indicated significantly reduced stress levels, accompanied by statistically significant improvements and a substantial effect size. However, it's important to acknowledge several limitations, including the absence of a control group, sample homogeneity, short intervention duration, and reliance on self-reported measures.

Nevertheless, these findings highlight MBAT's potential as an effective intervention for alleviating adolescent stress. Future research could explore the long-term benefits of extended MBAT interventions, address these limitations, and delve into the mechanisms underlying the observed stress reduction effects.

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